

Original Research Article

Psychiatric Morbidity Among the Children and Adolescents Attending Department of Psychiatry Tertiary Hospital in Nepal

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Abstract

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A variety of psychiatric manifestations can be seen in children and adolescent below the age of 19 years. This study aims to examine the socio-demographic, morbidity profiles, and clinical correlates of child and adolescent patients attending the psychiatry out-patient department of Lumbini Medical College and Teaching Hospital over a 1 year period. It is a retrospective case record analysis of all child and adolescent patients attending the psychiatry out-patient between Dec 1st 2018-Nov 30th 2019 in Lumbini Medical College and Teaching Hospital, Pravas, Palpa, Nepal. One hundred and forty cases attending the Outpatient department were analyzed. Females comprised 96 (68.6%) and males comprised 44(31.4%). Most of the patients (57.14%) were from 16-19 years group. Cases from urban areas (73 or 52.1% out of 140) predominated the picture. Psychiatric diagnoses was maximum for seizure disorder (33 or 23.6%) followed by conversion disorder(29 or 20.7%), then by depressive disorder (25 or 17.9%) and anxiety disorder (14 or 10% respectively). Majority of females had a diagnosis of conversion disorder (25 or 26%) followed by seizure disorder (23 or 24%), depressive disorder (15 or 15.6%) and anxiety disorder (7 or 7.3%) whereas among the males, most (10 or 22.7%) had the diagnosis of depressive disorder and seizure disorder equally followed by anxiety disorder (7 or 15.9%) and conversion disorder (4 or 9.1%) etc.

Keywords: Child and adolescents, Psychiatric morbidity, Retrospective study, Socio-demographic

INTRODUCTION

WHO statistics reveal that the prevalence of disabling mental illness among children and adolescence attending health care centers range between 20-30% in urban areas and 13-18% in rural areas (Hassan, 1991). Various studies from developing countries including Nepal and India show that a significant percentage (7-35%) of the pediatric population suffers from mental illness (Shrestha, 1986; Chadda and Saurabh, 1994; Regmi et al., 2000; Srinath et al., 2005; Shakya, 2010). Information regarding the morbidity profiles of these young patients would help to define needs and priorities.

It is estimated that 10-20% of children and adolescents are affected annually by psychiatric problems and their psychiatric morbidity accounts for 5 of the 10 leading causes of disability for those aged 5yrs and above. It has been found that mental and psychiatric services for children lag behind those for adults in developing countries (Murray and Lopez, 1996; Sawyer et al., 2001; Mc Kelvey et al., 2002; Sourander and Turunen, 1999; Eapen et al., 2001). Studies completed at various centers in Nepal show that a great majority of children and adolescents visit other setting of help-

Table 1. Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
F	96	68.6	68.6	68.6
M	44	31.4	31.4	100.0
Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Table 2. Age

Age in Years	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0-5	1	.7	.7	.7
6--10	8	5.71	5.71	5.71
11-15	51	36.42	36.42	36.42
16-19	80	57.14	57.14	57.14
Total	140	100.0	100.0	

Table 3. Locality
Locality (Urban/Rural)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Rural	67	47.9	47.9	47.9
	Urban	73	52.1	52.1	100.0
	Total	140	100.0	100.0	

seeking before coming to a psychiatric service for different psychological problems (Regmi et al., 2000; Shakya, 2010).

AIM OF THE STUDY

General-Information regarding the morbidity profiles of these young patients would help to define needs and priorities of them. It will also help to increase the awareness about these problems.

Specific-To assess the socio-demographic, morbidity profiles and clinical correlates of child and adolescents visiting the psychiatry Out Patient Department over a one year period (from Dec. 1st, 2018 to Nov. 30, 2019)

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was conducted at Lumbini Medical College and Teaching Hospital, Pravas, Palpa, Nepal. The inclusion criteria for this study were: complete chart analysis and case record of the patients and both sexes and age 19 yrs and below. Data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences, SPSS for window, version 20.

Procedure

A review of case record of all child and adolescent patients attending the Psychiatry Out-Patient Department

of LMCTH, Palpa between Dec. 1st 2018 to Nov 30, 2019 was carried out and information regarding socio-demographic characteristic (e. g age, gender, religion, domicile, and diagnosis) was recorded on a proforma designed by the authors. Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences, SPSS 20 for Windows. Cross tabulation, frequency statistics and chi square test were used for relationship between variables and the level of statistical significance was set at 5%.

RESULTS

A total of 140 child and adolescent patients had attended the psychiatry OPD during the period in review.

Majority (96 out of 140) of the patients were females (68.6%) while (44 out of 140) were males (31.4%). 80 out of 140 or 57.14% of the patients were between the ages 16-19 years followed by 11-15 years (36.42%) age group (Table 2).

Majority (73 or 52.1%) of the cases came from urban background (Table 3).

Table 4 shows the different psychiatric diagnosis which was maximum for seizure disorder (33 or 23.6%) followed by conversion disorder (29 or 20.7%), then by depressive disorder (25 or 17.9%) and anxiety disorder (14 or 10% respectively).

We also compared some of the diagnosis with gender (Table 5). When Seizure disorder, conversion disorder, depressive disorder and anxiety disorder were compared by gender using χ^2 -test, P-value was found to be non significant ($P > 0.001$).

Table 4. Psychiatric Diagnoses

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Acute Stress Reaction	3	2.1	2.1
Alcohol Dependent Syndrome	1	.7	.7
Anxiety Disorder	14	10.0	10.0
Cannabis induced Psychosis	1	.7	.7
Conversion Disorder	29	20.7	20.7
Deiberate Self Harm	2	1.4	1.4
Depressive Disorder	25	17.9	17.9
Manic Episode(F31)	1	.7	.7
Mental Retardation	1	.7	.7
Migraine Headache	3	2.1	2.1
Mixed Anxiety Depression	2	1.4	1.4
Mixed headache	1	.7	.7
MR with seizure disorder	1	.7	.7
Night Terror	1	.7	.7
Observation with admission	1	.7	.7
Post Partum Psychosis	2	1.4	1.4
Post Traumatic Stress Disorder	1	.7	.7
Psychiatric Dsorder NOS(F99)	1	.7	.7
Psychosis NOS	2	1.4	1.4
Recurrent Depressive disorder	2	1.4	1.4
Schizophrenia	5	3.6	3.6
Seizure Disorder	33	23.6	23.6
Somatoform Disorder	6	4.3	4.3
Tension Headache	1	.7	.7
Thyroid Disorder	1	.7	.7
Total	140	100.0	100.0

Table 5. Comparing Diagnosis with Gender

ICD-10 Psychiatric Diagnosis)		Gender		Total
		F	M	
Acute Stress Reaction	Count	1	2	3
	% within Gender	1.0%	4.5%	2.1%
Alcohol Dependency	Count	0	1	1
	% within Gender	0.0%	2.3%	0.7%
Anxiety Disorder	Count	7	7	14
	% within Gender	7.3%	15.9%	10.0%
Cannabis induced Psychosis	Count	0	1	1
	% within Gender	0.0%	2.3%	0.7%
Conversion Disorder	Count	25	4	29
	% within Gender	26.0%	9.1%	20.7%
Deiberate Self Harm	Count		2	2
	% within Gender	0.0%	4.54%	1.42%
Depressive Disorder	Count	15	10	25
	% within Gender	15.6%	22.7%	17.9%
Manic Episode(F31)	Count	0	1	1
	% within Gender	0.0%	2.3%	0.7%
Mental Retardation	Count	0	1	1
	% within Gender	0.0%	2.3%	0.7%
Migraine Headache	Count	3	0	3
	% within Gender	3.1%	0.0%	2.1%
Mixed Anxiety Depression	Count	2	0	2
	% within Gender			

Table 5. Continue

	% within Gender	2.1%	0.0%	1.4%
Mixed headache	Count	0	1	1
	% within Gender	0.0%	2.3%	0.7%
MR with seizure disorder	Count	1	0	1
	% within Gender	1.0%	0.0%	0.7%
Night Terror	Count	1	0	1
	% within Gender	1.0%	0.0%	0.7%
Observation with admission	Count	1	0	1
	% within Gender	1.0%	0.0%	0.7%
Post Partum Psychosis	Count	1	0	1
	% within Gender	1.0%	0.0%	0.7%
Post Traumatic Stress Disorder	Count	2	0	2
	% within Gender	2.08%	0.0%	1.42%
Psychiatric Disorder NOS(F99)	Count	1	0	1
	% within Gender	1.0%	0.0%	0.7%
Psychosis NOS	Count	0	2	2
	% within Gender	0.0%	4.5%	1.4%
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Recurrent Depressive disorder	Count	2	0	2
	% within Gender	2.1%	0.0%	1.4%
Schizophrenia	Count	4	1	5
	% within Gender	4.2%	2.3%	3.6%
Seizure Disorder	Count	23	10	33
	% within Gender	24.0%	22.7%	23.6%
Somatoform Disorder	Count	5	1	6
	% within Gender	5.2%	2.3%	4.3%
Tension Headache	Count	1	0	1
	% within Gender	1.0%	0.0%	0.7%
Thyroid Disorder	Count	1	0	1
	% within Gender	1.0%	0.0%	0.7%
Total	Count	96	44	140
	% within Gender	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Table 6. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	36.905 ^a	26	.076
Likelihood Ratio	43.254	26	.018
N of Valid Cases	140		

a. 47 cells (87.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .31.

Majority of females had a diagnosis of conversion disorder (25 or 26%) followed by seizure disorder (23 or 24%), depressive disorder (15 or 15.6%) and anxiety disorder (7 or 7.3%) whereas among the males, most (10 or 22.7%) had the diagnosis of depressive disorder and seizure disorder equally followed by anxiety disorder (7 or 15.9%) and conversion disorder (4 or 9.1%) etc. (Table 6)

DISCUSSION

The highest prevalence in terms of psychiatric disorders was in the 16-19 years group (57.14%) followed by 11-15 years age group (36.42%). The observed findings of female dominance (96 or 68.6%) in this study was similar to various studies. This finding was similar to the findings of Risal and Sharma (2010) which reported that (66.7%)

of the total study population was in the age group of 15-18 years and shows more female dominance (71.4%) than males (28.6%). 73 (52.1%) were from urban background and 67 (47.9%) were from rural background. Shakya (2010) also found that patients from urban areas were more prone to psychiatric illness. This may be due to less frustration tolerance and more stressful life in urban areas.

In this study the maximum number of patients were of seizure disorder (33 or 23.6%) which was maximum in female patients (24.0%). This finding is new may be because of the disorder firstly came to psychiatry OPD in our hospital rather than the Paediatric OPD. Then came conversion disorder 29 or 20.7%. This finding is comparable with the findings of Risal and Sharma (2010). This may be related to the possibilities that Nepali culture discourages direct expression of emotional distress and physical symptoms are a common ways of expressing psychological distress. Next came depressive disorder (25 or 17.9%) and this was more common in females (15.6%). Mental retardation was very less in our study (only total 2 cases out of 140 or 1.4%). This is quite paradox to the study done by Col S Chaudhur et al. (2007) in which the total cases of mental retardation were 10.5%. This may be due to most of the cases being primarily seen by the Paediatric department in our hospital. One interesting finding is that there were no cases of conduct disorder, ADHD, Autism, enuresis, somnambulism, trichotilomania, tic disorder etc which might be due to non referral of the cases from Paediatric OPD.

LIMITATIONS

There were some limitations in the study. Sample size is small. Study is confined to a tertiary hospital, which may not necessarily represent the general population of the country. Most of the case record were found to have incomplete data about educational qualification, socio-economic class, religion and hence could not be compared.

CONCLUSION

The majority of patients were in the age group 16-19 years, female sex, and from urban background. Commonest psychiatric diagnoses were seizure disorder (23.6%) followed by conversion disorder (20.7%), then by depressive disorder (17.9%) and anxiety disorder (10% respectively). There are fewer patients of younger ages. It indicates the need of raising awareness about psychological problems of this age groups. The observation that psychiatric morbidity is highest in the

age group (16-19 yrs) as revealed in this study may help in better planning of mental health services, with special focus towards these vulnerable age groups.

Further studies need to be using community-based surveys in a larger scale with appropriate sample size to find out the depth of the psychiatric problems in children. To conclude, LMCTH doesn't have a psychiatric OPD exclusively for children and adolescents but if such facilities were available, we would expect more patients attending the OPD.

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